

The fly *P. orbata* (see figure) is a small (4 mm long), black tachinid belonging to the tribe Siphonini. The tribe is characterized by minute prealar setae, very small size, head not sexually dimorphic, males and females with broad frons, two pairs of proclinate orbital setae, and strong outer vertical setae and thorax with strong subequal prostigmatic setae diverging from each other (particularly in *Peribaea*).

Parasitization was higher (6-19%) in unweeded sugarcane and ricefields containing *Rottboellia* and *Amaranthus* than in weeded fields (2%), suggesting that *P. orbata* is more effective at higher plant densities.

P. orbata is synonymous with *Actia monticola* Malloch and *A. rotundipennis* Malloch in the Philippines but previously had not been associated with any host. □

The tachinid fly *P. orbata* a) Head in frontal view, b) adult. Scale = 1 mm.

Rice insects and diseases in Goa, India

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No systematic survey of rice pests had been conducted in the Union Territory (UT) of Goa, Daman, and Diu. We monitored 6 locations in the north, 10 in the central, and 5 in the south at 3-wk intervals from mid-Jun to mid-Sep 1984. UT, 0.38 million ha in size, lies on the western coast of India. Rice, the main field crop, is on 54,000 ha, or 33.4% of the net area sown. The climate is warm humid tropical with temperatures around 17°C and 3 m annual rainfall.

Rice is cultivated primarily as a rainfed single crop. Irrigated rice is common only near springs, canals, and stream banks. Only 6% of area sown is cultivated more than once per year. Rice is a second crop Nov-Feb on only about 3,000 ha with assured irrigation.

Rice - groundnut, rice - pulses, and rice - vegetables are other common cropping patterns. About 80% of total

Rice pests and their intensity in Goa, India, 1984.

	Intensity (%)
<i>Insects</i>	
<i>Hieroglyphus</i> spp.	23
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	15
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	10
<i>Hydrellia</i> spp.	7
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i>	7
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i>	6
<i>Leptocorisa acuta</i>	5
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	5
<i>Stenchaetothrips bififormis</i>	4
<i>Dicladispa armigera</i>	4
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i>	2
<i>Leptispa pygmoea</i>	1
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	1
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>	0.5
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0.4
<i>Brevienia rehi</i>	0.2
<i>Pathogens</i>	
<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i>	15
<i>Cochliobolus miyabeanus</i>	6
<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	3
<i>Rhynchosporium oryzae</i>	1
<i>Thanatephorus cucumeris</i>	1
<i>Xanthomonas translucens</i> f. sp. <i>oryzicola</i>	1
<i>Acrocyllidium oryzae</i>	1
<i>Ustilagoidea virens</i>	1

area under rice is planted to high yielding varieties Vikram, IET6080, Govinda, Jaya, Jothi, and Annapurna.

Pest levels and rice crop damage were recorded from 2 fixed plots at each survey site, 100 m back of each side of the road, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale. Average damage intensity was computed for each insect and disease found.

Eight diseases and 16 insects were found (see table). The survey indicated a shift in importance in insects, from *Scirpophaga incertulas* to *Hieroglyphus banian* and *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. The major disease problem was *Xanthomonas oryzae*. *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* was more important than *Pyricularia oryzae*. □

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